

Attitude effects on the observed orientation angle of HF waves from the Radio Receiver Instrument on e-POP/Swarm-E

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ABSTRACT

The Radio Receiver Instrument (RRI) on e-POP/Swarm-E has a cross-dipole antenna capable of observing HF radio waves. Slew-to-transmitter passes, in which the antenna boresight direction is aligned with the ray direction are the ideal cases to observe the full polarization ellipse. From the voltages on the dipoles, the polarization characteristics, such as the ellipticity angle and the orientation angle can be determined. However, the RRI may not always be in an optimum position to observe the full signal. In such cases, the polarization characteristics cannot be fully captured. The effects of dipole boresight pointing on the observed orientation angle variations during Faraday rotation periods are presented in detail.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ionosphere affects radio waves in complex ways due to the presence of the Earth's magnetic field. Specifically, the O- and X-mode waves that make up the combined wave have different refractive indices, resulting in different propagation speeds for the wave modes [1]. As a result, an incoming radio wave may appear to rotate when the angle between the magnetic field and the wave's propagation direction (known as the aspect angle) is favourable in Quasi-Longitudinal (QL) regime. This rotation is known as Faraday rotation and is characterized by the wrapping of the orientation angle from 0° to 180° (or 180° to 0°). Circular waves may be observed more frequently when the ray propagation direction is perpendicular to the magnetic field at aspect angles close to 90° in Quasi-Transverse (QT) regime. In some special cases as in [2] only one mode may reach the spacecraft when one of the modes gets bent close to its cut-off frequency, displaying circular wave characteristics even when aspect angle is not close to 90° .

Transionospheric experiments hold a crucial role in understanding how a transmitted signal behaves when traversing an inhomogeneous plasma medium. Experiments between ground-based transmitters and receivers on satellites assist in exploring the characteristics of HF radio waves. In 2013, the e-POP suite was launched onboard the Swarm-E (previously known as CASSIOPE) satellite. The suite carried the Radio Receiver Instrument (RRI) as one of its eight instruments, which is a digital receiver that can detect waves between 10 Hz and 18 MHz [3].

Swarm-E was capable of slewing to a specific target, whether on the ground or in the ionosphere. Optimum observation conditions were attained when RRI boresight was aligned with the radio wave propagation direction. A series of coordinated slew-to-transmitter experiments were conducted in April 2016 to investigate the polarization characteristics of HF radio waves between the NRCan Ottawa transmitter and RRI. Danskin et al. [4] presented clear evidence of Faraday rotation for a wide range of aspect angles above 100° during the experiments, especially southward of the Ottawa transmitter.

However, manoeuvring constraints and other instrument's optimal attitude occasionally prevented slew-to-target mode for RRI-ground transmitter conjunctions. For some experiments, RRI boresight had different pointing directions, such as ram (along the spacecraft trajectory) and Nadir (downward to the center of the Earth). Since RRI boresight did not align fully with the signal propagation direction, the attitude modes other than slew-to-transmitter led to insufficient alignment for observations of the polarization characteristics of the complete wave. Previously, Eyiguler et al. [5] presented an overview of how the power, ellipticity angle, and orientation angle varied during a slew-to-transmitter and a ram pass. The present paper presents a thorough investigation on how antenna boresight impacts the orientation angle for individual sequences.

2. DATA and METHODS

RRI has two 6 m dipoles, which are orthogonal to each other and rotated from the spacecraft +Y axis by $\pm 45^\circ$. RRI samples the complex voltages induced on its dipoles in response to natural or artificial wave emission sources at a rate of 62.5 kHz. With RRI's complex voltage sampling capabilities, mathematical methods, such as the Stokes parameter approach can be utilized to obtain the polarization characteristics of radio waves. The Stokes parameters approach has the assumption that the polarization ellipse of the radio wave is fully projected onto the plane of dipoles, which occurs when the radio wave is perpendicular to the plane of dipoles [6, 4].

Three experiments between RRI and NRCan Ottawa transmitter are selected to show the effect on the orientation angle observations. The transmitter operated at 6.9285 MHz during the experiments on 13 May 2017, 14 July 2017, and 15 July 2017. The signal consisted of a continuous wave (CW) transmission of 0.9 seconds and a binary phase shift keying (BPSK) transmission of 7 seconds. The CW transmission started at each 10 second boundary followed by a pause of 1.1 seconds between the CW and BPSK transmissions. Millstone Hill digisonde determined foF2 to be 4.3, 5.2 and 5.1 MHz for 13 May, 14 July and July, respectively. hmF2 was reported to be 182, 229 and 223 km, respectively. Ionograms are available at (<https://giro.uml.edu/didbase/>). Swarm-E was at an altitude of ~ 500 km, and ~ 400 km for the experiments on 13 May and 14-15 July, above the F2 peak by at least ~ 180 km.

Quaternions were used to calculate the RRI boresight and directions of the individual dipole axis for the selected experiments. RRI and quaternion data files are available from the Swarm-E web site (<https://epop-data.phys.ucalgary.ca/>). The complementary reception angle (hereafter abbreviated as CRA) shows the degree of deviation from the optimum observation condition for a dipole. CRAs were calculated for each dipole by subtracting the angle between the line-of-sight ray propagation direction and dipole's axis (reception angle) from 90° . A CRA of 0° indicates perfect alignment, whereas $\pm 90^\circ$ denotes end-of-dipole alignment. In the current study, intervals with RRI boresight pointing along the satellite trajectory were classified as RRI-ram, along the Nadir direction as RRI-Nadir, and to the transmitter as slew-to-transmitter.

3. OBSERVATION and INTERPRETATIONS

Figure 1 shows a sequence during a slew-to-transmitter experiment on 13 May 2017. Swarm-E was in the East of Ottawa, going from South to North. The first panel displays the power on dipole1 (red), dipole2 (cyan), and the total power (black). The complementary reception angles are denoted as θ_{CD1} and θ_{CD2} in the middle panel. The orientation angle is shown in the bottom panel. Geodetic altitude, geographic latitude, geographic longitude, aspect angle, and distance from Ottawa (R) are given as secondary axes below the time axis. The sketch on the right of Figure 1 illustrates the geometry between the dipole axes (red for dipole 1 and cyan for dipole 2), RRI boresight (black) and incident ray vector (blue) at the timing of the sequence in the left part. Light blue dashed line depicts the line-of-sight (LOS) path from the transmitter to the RRI.

On 13 May 2017, between 17:29:21 and 17:29:29 the dipoles' power had similar, alternating amplitude, nearly reaching the background signal levels as shown in Figure 1. The total power remained constant during the sequence. Power observations of similar amplitudes suggests that x and y components of the polarization ellipse were observed equally well. θ_{CD1} and θ_{CD2} were very close to 0° indicating that the ray was nearly perpendicular to the dipole plane. Aspect angle was between 132° to 129° . Consequently, the orientation angle changed from 180° to 0° in the form of a straight line depicting full Faraday rotation, which is consistent with the findings of Danskin et al. [4].

Figure 1: Slew-to-transmitter experiment on 13 May 2017. Left: Top panel shows the powers on dipoles: dipole1, red; dipole2, cyan and total power in black. The Complementary reception angles are displayed in middle panel; red and cyan for dipole1 and dipole2, respectively. Bottom panel shows the variation of the orientation angle. Geodetic altitude, geographic latitude, geographic longitude, aspect angle, and distance from Ottawa (R) are given as secondary axes below the time axis shown on the bottom panel. Right: Diagram showing the geometry between the dipole axes (red for dipole 1 and cyan for dipole 2), RRI boresight (black) and incoming ray vector (blue) at the timing of the sequence. Ottawa is shown with a circle at the bottom. Light blue dashed line is the line-of-sight (LOS) path from the transmitter to the RRI.

The diagram on the right of Figure 1 confirms that ray was perpendicular to the dipole plane and RRI boresight was aligned parallel to the LOS ray path, which can be observed from θ_{CD1} and θ_{CD2} on the second panel of the figure. Hence, the sequence can be exemplified as an ideal slew-to-transmitter sequence.

Figure 2 shows a sequence, in which geometry between the spacecraft and RRI antenna enabled only one dipole to have favourable observation condition during the 14 July experiment. θ_{CD1} was around 18° whereas θ_{CD2} was as high as 89° . Hence, the power on dipole 2 was one order of magnitude smaller than the power on dipole 1. Dipole 1 had the largest contribution to the total power. The orientation angle was confined between 165° and 180° throughout the sequence and was not wrapping as was observed in the slew-to-transmitter case. Sketch on the right demonstrates that the ray hit dipole1 axis perpendicularly, however it was edge-on and parallel to dipole2 axis.

Figure 2: Same as Figure 1, but for the RRI-ram on 14 July 2017.

Figure 3 shows a unique experiment, in which geometry crippled both dipoles' ability to observe the transmitted signal between 19:50:30 and 19:50:40 on 15 July 2017. The spacecraft was in the East of Ottawa, but a mere 0.1° geographic longitude away from the transmitter making the experiment a nearly overhead pass. θ_{CD1} and θ_{CD2} were above 60° during the sequence indicating that most of the polarization ellipse was not observed. Equal order of magnitude powers on dipole1 and dipole2 did not alternate and Faraday rotation was not visible as expected from the Faraday rotation periods around 165° aspect angle. Rather, orientation angle was stable and oscillated with small amplitudes around 135° as would be expected from an observation of a circular wave. If CRAs are not considered, the sequence can easily be misinterpreted as an example observation of one mode reaching the spacecraft. However, as seen in the diagram on the right, ray was near-perfectly parallel to the dipole plane, and edge-on to the dipole axes leading to insufficient measurement of the components of the polarization ellipse.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 1, but for the RRI-ram near-overhead pass on 15 July 2017. In addition to the examples, a RRI-Nadir pass (not shown here) displays power and orientation angle variations similar to a RRI-ram pass at the start and end of a flyby. Poor geometry between the ray propagation direction and the dipole axes leads to high CRAs at the start and the end. However, when the satellite draws closer to the transmitter nearing the point of the closest approach, CRAs may become as low as 0° (if the pass is overhead RRI-Nadir). Hence, powers on dipoles become similar order of magnitude and clear Faraday rotation signatures should be visible, resulting in a mimicking of a slew-to-transmitter experiment. After the point of the closest approach, the dipoles gradually lose capability to capture radio waves as the CRAs rise and the radio wave is no longer perpendicular to the dipole plane. The true polarization characteristics cannot be easily determined as was observed in RRI-ram pass.

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of antenna boresight pointing on the powers induced at RRI dipoles and the observed/computed orientation angle for Faraday rotation regime intervals was studied for two different satellite attitudes. The sequence during the slew-to-transmitter pass on 13 May 2017 illustrated the expected Faraday rotation signatures for radio wave propagating predominantly parallel to the magnetic field. On the other hand, Faraday rotation was not apparent in the measurements on 14-15 July 2017. The overhead RRI-ram pass on 15 July 2017 could be easily mistaken as one-mode reaching the spacecraft, expressing the importance of taking CRAs into account in the interpretation of the estimated polarization characteristics. Findings reported in this paper strongly suggest that a three-axis dipole is needed to fully resolve the signal for unfavourable satellite attitude modes. A three-axis dipole configuration would provide the opportunity to eliminate geometry effects on the observed/computed polarization characteristics and would allow the reconstruction of the original signal for any attitude mode.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Gillies, R. G., G. C. Hussey, G. J. Sofko, and H. G. James (2012), Modeling measurements of ionospheric density structures using the polarization of high-frequency waves detected by the Radio Receiver Instrument on the enhanced Polar Outflow Probe, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117, A04316, doi:10.1029/2011JA017457.
- [2] Pandey, K., Eyiguler, E. C. K., Gillies, R. G., Hussey, G. C., Danskin, D. W., & Yau, A. W. (2022). Polarization characteristics of a single mode radio wave traversing through the ionosphere: A unique observation from the RRI on ePOP/SWARM-E. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 127, e2022JA030684. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JA030684>
- [3] Yau, A. W., & James, H. G. (2015). CASSIOPE enhanced polar outflow probe (e-POP) mission overview. *Space Science Reviews*, 189(1), 3-14.
- [4] Danskin, D. W., Hussey, G. C., Gillies, R. G., James, H. G., Fairbairn, D. T., & Yau, A. W. (2018). Polarization Characteristics Inferred from the Radio Receiver Instrument on the Enhanced Polar Outflow Probe. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 123(2), 1648–1662. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JA024731>
- [5] Eyiguler, E. C. K., Danskin, D. W., Hussey, G. C., Pandey, K., Gillies, R. G., & Yau, A. W. (2022, May). Satellite attitude effects on the reception of transionospheric HF signals: Examples from the Radio Receiver Instrument onboard e-POP/Swarm-E. In *2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [6] Born, M., & Wolf, E. (1980). *Principles of optics: Electromagnetic theory of propagation, interference and diffraction of light* (6th ed.). Oxford, UK: Pergamon Press.